

European Swine Influenza Network - swIAV Evolution and Diversity in Europe

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Introduction

Swine Influenza A viruses (swIAV) are prevalent among pigs in Europe and pose a significant threat to human health due to their zoonotic transmission and pandemic potentials. The intensification of pig production systems and the unrestricted movement of live swine may the spread of swIAV in Europe across national borders. Surveillance of swIAV evolution in Europe plays a crucial role in early detection of potential zoonotic pandemic strains, facilitates informed decision-making in vaccine candidate selection, and enhances overall public and veterinary health preparedness.

Recognizing the importance of coordinated efforts, the European Swine Influenza Network (ESFLU) has been established as a COST Action scientific network. Its primary objective is to foster scientific collaboration and enhance capacity at the European level for monitoring the evolution and spread of swIAVs, as well as identifying measures to prevent the spread of swIAVs within and between European countries. A pivotal component of ESFLU activities is the task undertaken by Working Group (WG) 2, which involves the biannual compilation of a report detailing the evolution of swIAVs in Europe. This report is the result of collaborative efforts with ESFLU WG2 members sharing swIAV sequences derived from samples collected and sequenced between October 2022 and September 2023, the initial period of the ESFLU COST Action. To achieve this, rigorous phylogenetic analyses were conducted on the compiled sequences and the results were made available online through a Nextstrain instance (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/esflu>). These analyses sought to determine the diversity of swIAVs in specific countries and their respective proportions based on the classification and analysis of HA sequences and NA sequences. Moreover, the analyses aimed to ascertain whether certain viruses had potentially traversed national boundaries, indicating the cross-border movement of these viruses.

ESFLU WG2 also provides a crucial connection between ESFLU and OFFLU, the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) / Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) network of expertise on animal influenza. OFFLU performs biannual analyses of swIAVs circulating globally with the aim of identifying candidate vaccine viruses for pandemic preparedness (<https://www.offlu.org/index.php/offlu-vcv-summary-reports/>). As part of this activity, WG2 will assist in the sharing of swIAV sequences between ESFLU members and OFFLU to facilitate increased resolution of swIAV diversity within ESFLU member countries. As such, this will help increase the outputs of ESFLU at the international level.

Regular updates of this nature are paramount for staying ahead of potential public and veterinary health threats. By continuously monitoring swIAV evolution in Europe, ESFLU WG2 reports endeavor to provide timely information to support enhanced preparedness of public health systems at the European level concerning swIAVs.

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Methods

The collected sequences were checked for their quality by removing sequences with more than 10 undetermined nucleotides (N) using `seqkit grep -s -r -v -p NNNNNNNNNN` (Shen et al. 2016). Hemagglutinin (HA) sequence clades were assigned using the BV-BRC Subspecies Classification webserver with the swine influenza H1 global classification (Olson et al. 2023). Neuraminidase (NA) clades were assigned by BLASTing the sequences against a reference set of annotated N1 Eurasian-Avian-like (EA), N1 pandemic 2009 (pdm), N2 'Gent' and N2 'Scotland' reference sequences. HA and NA sequences were aligned separately using `mafft --auto` (Kato and Standley 2013). A time-scaled phylogeny was computed for the HA gene using the Nextstrain auspice pipeline (Hadfield et al. 2018) based on IQTREE2 (Minh et al. 2020) and TreeTime (Sagulenko, Puller, and Neher 2018) (Figure 1). Maximum-Likelihood phylogenetic trees (Figure 2) were computed using `iqtree2 -B 1000 -nm 1000 --alrt 1000 --seqtype DNA -nt AUTO` for both HA and NA genes. The resulting trees were plotted with automatic color attribution based on the country of origin of sequences using a custom R script based on the ggtree R package (Yu et al. 2016).

Results

In total, we received and analysed 1749 swIAV sequences from 16 countries which corresponded to about 249 unique strains, with 12 H3 strains and 236 H1 strains. Summary statistics concerning the metadata of the received sequences are shown in Table 1. After the determination of the HA clade of each collected sequence using the BV-BRC webserver, the Nextstrain pipeline was applied to the collected HA sequences and revealed that each country appears to have their own combination of swIAVs HA clades in different proportions (Figure 1). According to the collected filtered data, the most dominant swIAVs were from the H1 HA clades: 1C.2.4 (75 sequences), 1A.3.3.2 (63 sequences), 1C.2.1 (40 sequences) and 1C.2.2 (27 sequences) (Figure 1.A). This followed the trend of the countries that shared the most sequences, i.e. Denmark, France, Italy and Germany, which may have led to a bias in the summation. These HA clades were still the most represented in terms of presence/absence in European countries, with 1C.2.4 found in six countries; 1A.3.3.2 and 1C.2.2 both found in seven countries; and 1C.2.1 found in nine countries (Figure 1.B), out of the 16 countries covered by the dataset. Additionally, six H1 1C.2.5 swIAV sequences were reported, in Denmark, Italy, Poland, and Greece. Their presence in Denmark and Italy had already been reported in the January to June 2023 OFFLU report (<https://www.offlu.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/OFFLU-vcn-swine-2023b.pdf>), and we here show the presence of the 1C.2.5 clade in two other European countries: Poland and Greece. On the other hand, some clades were specific to certain countries, like the H1 1B.1.1 clade that was only detected in the United Kingdom. Moreover, a sequence from Finland was found to show little resemblance with other sequences of the 1C clade. BLAST analyses on public databases revealed that this Finnish sequence is close to other sequences from Finland collected before 2010, thus highlighting a potential HA clade specifically circulating in Finland. This however needs to be confirmed with a larger set of sequences spanning decades of swIAVs evolution.

Table 1: Collected sequences metadata statistics. The collection date corresponds to at least month and year.

Segment	Number of collected sequences	Complete coding sequences	Number of sequences with collection dates	Number of sequences with region of origin
HA	249	249	186	67
NA	247	247	186	67
PB2	207	207	152	65
PB1	206	206	146	64
PA	205	205	152	67
NP	211	211	150	67
NS	213	213	150	67
MP	212	212	150	67

In addition to the H1 swIAVs, 12 H3 swIAV sequences were shared concerning seven countries: Denmark, Germany, Italy, North Macedonia, the Netherlands, Spain and Ukraine. Of the sequences that could be classified into the H3 clades (N=10), the 'Other-Human-2020' clade is predominant with five sequences from three countries: Denmark, Germany and North Macedonia. This is followed by two 'Other-Human-2020-like' detected in Ukraine. This is concerning since this most likely corresponds to relatively recent human to swine H3N2 IAV viruses transmissions that potentially started

to circulate in pigs, which needs to be confirmed with more sequences. This is followed by the two sequences from the ‘2000.3’ clade detected in the Netherlands and Spain. The ‘1970.1’ H3 clade was only identified in a single sequence obtained from Italy. 1970.1 and 2000.3 clades correspond to old transmissions from human to swine that circulate in pigs since decades. Overall, H3 detections were substantially lower than H1 swIAVs, which is representative of what has been previously observed at the European level but highlights the need for continued surveillance (Simon et al. 2014; Henritzi et al. 2020).

The Maximum-Likelihood trees coloured by countries (Figure 2) reveal that in each HA clade, swIAVs tend to evolve separately in each country further confirming the results of Figure 1 and suggesting separate evolution of swIAVs within each European country. However, we can observe that certain country-specific genogroups display potential swIAVs transfers from one country to another, indicated by the blue stars in Figure 2. For instance, potential transfers are observed between Denmark and Germany (Figure 2A), France and Denmark, and potentially between Belgium and Germany (Figure 2B).

Since there is no official NA classification for swIAV yet, no detailed evolution discussion is provided for this segment. However, we can see that like the HA, the NA segment tend to evolve within each country. The potential transfers of swIAV strains from one country to another observed in the HA trees are confirmed in the NA tree (Figure 3), with an H1 1A.3.3.2 N1 Eurasian-Avian like between Denmark to Germany (Figure 3A), an H1 1C.2.4 N2 Gent between France and Denmark (Figure 3B), and potentially an H1 1A.3.3.2 N2 Gent between Belgium and Germany (Figure 3B).

Figure 1: Nextstrain results of the collected swIAVs sequences. (A) Time-scaled phylogeny of the HA gene, sequences are colored by clade. (B) Map of Europe displaying the proportions of the analysed swIAV HA clades in each country. The size of each pie chart and segments therein correspond to the number of sequences analysed in the associated country, which is displayed in the top left-hand corner. The most dominant HA clades per country are displayed within (in white) or near (in black) the associated pie chart. Interactive versions of the plots are available on the ESFLU Nextstrain instance: <https://nextstrain.org/groups/ESFLU/swIAV/HA-10-2022-09-2023>.

Figure 2: Maximum-Likelihood phylogenetic trees for the HA segment of the collected swIAV sequences in Europe. One phylogeny was made with all the sequences and was subsequently separated into four phylogenetic trees following the H1 1A (A), 1B (B), 1C (C) and H3 (D) HA clades. Blue stars indicate potential swIAV transfers from one country to another, based on the identification of sequences from one country encompassed within a genogroup from another country. Interactive versions of the plots are available on the ESFLU Nextstrain instance: <https://nextstrain.org/groups/ESFLU/swIAV/HA-10-2022-09-2023>.

Figure 3: Maximum-Likelihood phylogenetic trees for the NA gene of the collected swIAV sequences in Europe. Since no official classification exists for swIAV NA genes, clades have been assigned automatically by BLAST using N1 Eurasian-avian-like (EA), N1 pandemic 2009 (pdm), N2 Gent and N2 Scotland reference sequences and are indicated at the end of the taxon labels. Blue stars indicate potential swIAV transfers from one country to another corresponding to such potential cases highlighted on the HA trees (Figure 2). Interactive versions of the plots are available on the ESFLU Nextstrain instance: <https://nextstrain.org/groups/ESFLU/swIAV/NA-10-2022-09-2023>.

Discussion and conclusion

This first report of the European Swine Influenza Network (ESFLU) COST Action allows the swine influenza community to better assess the evolution of swIAVs in Europe with an up-to-date snapshot of the swIAV diversity from the end of 2022 to the end of 2023 over 16 European countries. Based on the analysis and classification of the collected HA sequences, we could observe that some HA clades tend to be more represented in Europe, with each country displaying a specific set of viruses in specific proportions, which agrees with previously published studies at the European level (Watson et al. 2015; Simon et al. 2014; Henritzi et al. 2020). Phylogenetic analyses showed that swIAVs tend to evolve separately within each country, suggesting that swIAVs mainly spread at a local scale / within country scale. This can be explained since live pigs movements happen mainly within local areas for small-scale production systems or between farms belonging to the same company (which are rarely cross-country) in intensive and extensive production systems, according to modelling based on real-world domestic pig movement networks from 3 European countries (Relun et al. 2017). However, potential transfers of swIAVs from country to country have been observed over this one-year period within the 1C.2.4 and 1A.3.3.2 H1 clades, some of the most widespread swIAVs clades in Europe, which may be explained by the long-distance live swine trade that does exist in Europe (Trovao and Nelson 2020). New data collected over the course of the ESFLU COST Action will allow for enhanced monitoring of the potential cross-country infections, allowing a better understanding of swIAV evolution and dissemination dynamics over Europe. This work will therefore substantially contribute to enhanced preparedness and response strategies at the European level for swine influenza dissemination and the potential knock-on effects that may result in the public health sphere.

Citation

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